
THE CONCEPT OF EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE MILITARY-PATRIOTIC SPIRIT

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Abstract.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the organizational and legal foundations of the preliminary training and military-patriotic education of young people before conscription were created. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Laws "On Defense", "General Military Obligation" and "On Military Service", "Concept of Education of Youth in the Spirit of Military-Patriotism" and "Defense Doctrine" Uzbekistan Republic, "Oath to the Motherland", general military regulations and regulatory documents of state bodies and ministries in this field were adopted. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 348 of December 18, 2014 "On further improvement of the system of training the youth of the Republic of Uzbekistan for military service" was approved. Based on the appendix to this decision, the regulation "On the organization of initial training before the call and the procedure for its conduct" was developed.

Key words.

Cabinet of Ministers, preliminary training before conscription, documents, Defense doctrine, Education of youth in the spirit of military patriotism, regulations, decisions.

To the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 140 dated February 23, 2018

Appendix 1

Chapter 1. General rules

1. The concept of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit (hereinafter referred to as the concept) was developed based on the priorities and main principles of the state policy regarding youth implemented in our country. mutual cooperation determines the actual tasks related to educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit and ways to solve them, taking into account the role and importance of state and non-state non-profit organizations, family, neighborhood, educational institutions in this regard .

2. In this concept, based on the requirements of the Strategy of Actions, the issue of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit is considered as an

integral and integral part of the holistic education system related to raising a physically and mentally healthy generation. National and special attention was paid to the issue of developing the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, harmonizing it with world best practices and real socio-political changes in the life of Uzbekistan today.

3. By inculcating the most important concepts, life and professional skills in the hearts and minds of young people on the basis of science and knowledge, to protect our Motherland like the apple of an eye, to promote its beauty to the world. childhood, educating patriotic citizens as truly Uzbeks is the main content of the Concept.

4. Educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism is a state aimed at forming a sense of loyalty to the Motherland in young people, regardless of nationality, language and profession, and educating them as individuals capable of fulfilling their civil and constitutional duties. obligations, protecting the interests of society and the state. It is a multi-level, systematic, targeted and coordinated activity of bodies, public associations and other organizations.

Chapter 2. The purpose and main tasks of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit.

5. The purpose of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism. Young people should be active in various branches of society, especially in the types of public service related to the military sector, be loyal to the Constitution and military duty in peacetime and military conditions, and in them, their country and is to form important features such as high responsibility and accountability for the fate of the people.

6. The following are the main tasks of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit:

Educating young people in the spirit of national ideals and loyalty to the Motherland, instilling in their hearts and minds that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty;

to be proud of our ancient history and culture, our national heroes who selflessly fought for the independence and development of our beloved Motherland, to form a sense of being worthy of them, to strengthen confidence in the power and potential of our national army;

strengthening the understanding that military service is a sacred duty for every citizen of Uzbekistan, as well as theoretical and practical skills for our national army;

To form in young people the skills to approach the political and social processes taking place around us and in the world based on our national interests, and to form ideological immunity against various internal and external threats;

Educating young people with the ability to make quick and independent decisions in any complex situation, to effectively use modern military equipment;

To be ready to protect the interests of Uzbekistan not only in the military sphere, but also in all aspects of life, to be selfless for the country - this is the demand of today, to inculcate in the minds of the youth through real examples and effective means.

Chapter 3. The system of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit and its main principles.

7. The system of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit is a continuous process, which consists of a complex of interrelated political-legal, socio-economic, ideological-ideological, cultural-educational activities.

8. Education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, general military regulations of the Armed Forces and other laws will be conducted in accordance with the documents.

9. Education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit is regularly organized on a systematic and scientific basis.

10. The system of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit consists of the following:

pre-school education, general secondary education, vocational training and higher education institutions aimed at forming and developing the values of socio-spiritual importance, the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland in the educational process;

11. The following are the main principles of educating young people in the military-patriotic spirit;

scientificity;

historicity;

accuracy and speed;

regularity;

activity;

harmony of education and training;

consistency of the educational process;
relying on positive results and achievements in military-patriotic education.

REFERENCES:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. March 24, 2003.
2. A. Olmasov, M. Sharifhojaev. Economic theory. T. 1995 u.
3. A. Olmasov, A. Wahabov. Economic theory. T.: East. 2006.
4. D. Tojiboeva. Economic theory. Part I. T. 2002.
5. D. Tojiboeva. Economic theory. Part P. T. 2003.
6. N. Beknozov. Economic theory. / / Textbook. - T. 2005 u. 14. U. Umarov. Economic theory. / / Tutorial. T.: Heritage. 2004.
7. Sh. Shodmonov, R. Alimov, T. Joraev Economic theory. T. 2002.
8. Sh. Shodmonov, U.V. Gafurov. Economic theory. T. 2005 u.
9. Economics of Uzbekistan. Informatsionno-analiticheskiy obzor za 2005 god. T.: Uzbekistan. 2006.
10. Lex.uz website.